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Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
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Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
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Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)

23 August 2023

Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics)

This is being self-declared that Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has twelve years & eight months duration (full time) academic research, professional research, teaching experiences and research supervision in different reputed universities, textiles industries & related research organizations in an international platform dated on 23 August 2023. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is an inventor of “camouflage physics” for color engineering, camouflage engineering and camouflage textiles. He has sole author contributions of research & publication through PhD (Fashion & Textiles), School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020-2023.

23/08/2023

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

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Attached scanned copies of certificates and evidences

Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anowar Hossain.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8196694>

Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Md. Anowar Hossain.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8196696>

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Cite

Md. Anowar Hossain, Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics)

Principle of Anowar's life Journey through PhD education

“Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world.”